

NON-ENROLMENT AND DROP-OUT OF SLUM CHILDREN IN SCHOOLS: AN EXPLORATORY ANALYSIS OF JAMIA NAGAR LOCALITY

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Abstract

Slums are a universal phenomenon and exist in almost all cities across the world. The under privileged children residing in the slums are deprived of various basic amenities that the non-slum children in general do enjoy so they need special attention. As per 2011 Census report in India roughly 1.37 crore households or 17.4% of urban households lived in slums. Education plays a pivotal role in laying a proper foundation for the over-all socio-economic development of any region. Right of Children to Free and Compulsory Education Act 2009 provides children the right to free and compulsory admission, attendance and completion of elementary education. This study tries to explore the impact of living condition, home and surrounding environment, parental education, school condition on elementary education of slum children in Jamia Nagar Locality of 6-14 years age group. Convenient sampling technique was adopted. Data were collected from 40 parents in all: 20 parents of non-enrolled children and 20 parents of dropout children through a socio-economic status schedule and interview schedule. Qualitative analysis was done. It was found that migration, health, nature of occupation of the family, mother's level of education, per-capita income of the family, living condition, home and surrounding environment, school infra-structure has a positive impact on child's education.

Key Words: Non-Enrolment, Drop-Out, Slum Children

INTRODUCTION

Urbanization accompanied by sustained population growth due to large scale migration leads to mushrooming slum settlement. Thus, slums are a universal phenomenon and exist practically in almost all cities across the world. About 828 million or 33% of the urban population of developing countries resides in slums. Sub-Saharan Africa consists of about 62% urban population living in slums. In Asia, the proportion of urban population living in slums varies from 25% in western Asia to 35% in south Asia. In Latin America and the Caribbean slum prevalence is 24%. (UN-Habitat 2010).

In India roughly 1.37 crore households or 17.4% of urban households lived in slums which means nearly 1 in every 6 urban households lived in slums. Over a third of India's slum population lives in its 46 million plus cities. Of the four metro cities Mumbai has the highest proportion of slum dwelling households (41.3%) followed by Kolkata and Chennai (29.6 and 28.5 % respectively). Delhi, the capital of India has 14.6% of its households living in slums. Among all million plus cities Vishakhapatnam has the highest population of slum dwellers (44.1%). Decadal growth over the period 2001-11 shows that population has increased by more than 181 million, % of growth is 17.64, literacy has gone up from 64.83% to 74.04% and slum population has increased from 75.26 million to 93.06 million. (Census 2011).

The concept of slum and its definition may slightly vary depending upon the socioeconomic condition or local perception prevailing in the society but the general physical characteristics of most of the slums are found to be essentially same world-wide. Slums are usually a cluster of hutments with dilapidated and unstable structures having common toilet, lack of basic amenities, inadequate arrangement of drainage and disposal of solid waste and garbage (GOI report on Slum Population, 2005). Slums are highly unhygienic and disease prone. These areas are also breeding ground for various anti-social activities like crime, theft, burglary, and drug-addiction and so on. Slums in particular have been observed to have very low socio-economic status, low literacy levels and limited access to

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primary education facilities. Traditional approaches to impart primary education have been found grossly inadequate in view of the prevailing socio-economic and cultural background of the slum areas.

It is observed that education plays a pivotal role in laying a proper foundation for the over-all socioeconomic development of any region. Education is considered as one of the principal means to foster deeper and more harmonious form of human development and thereby to reduce poverty, exclusion, ignorance, oppression and war (Dellor Commission, 1996). In India since Independence (1947) several initiatives have been taken for qualitative and quantitative expansion of elementary education like operation black-board, DPEP, SSA, mid-day meal scheme and many others , one of the latest being RTE. The RTE Act 2009 provides a justifiable legal framework that entitles all children between the ages of 6-14 years to an education of reasonable quality, based on the principles of equity and non-discrimination. It provides children right to free and compulsory admission, attendance and completion of elementary education. Standing at this juncture it is absolutely necessary to understand and evaluate the present scenario of slum children in regard to access, retention and completion of elementary education of satisfactory quality.

Universal elementary education (UEE) is necessary for accelerating India's economic growth. Children from poor families after acquiring basic skills can participate in economic development in a better manner and can reap the benefit of health and family welfare programmes. However it is unfortunate that even after more than six decades of independence, we have not been able to achieve the goal of universal elementary education (UEE) even in Delhi, the national capital of India.

A significant proportion of the children in Delhi, who are not going to schools, belong to the slum areas. Slums in Delhi have been growing very fast in the last few years. These areas are characterized by low income, large family, low literacy rates and lack of basic facilities. Birth and death rates are highest here resulting in lower economic productivity and lower standards of living. Problems of hunger, under nutrition and associated disorders are the striking features of these areas.

EDUCATIONAL BACKWARDNESS OF SLUMS

Whereas cities generally have better schooling facilities and relatively a higher rate of adult literacy than the other areas of a region, city, slums may hold population that are backward in education and literacy. The typical picture of an Indian city slum is that of children of the school going age wandering about on their own, playing marbles or search games. Some of them, of course, help their parents in their work and in looking after their younger children. There are others who try to have their own means of livelihood by working as shoe-shiners, shop/hotel boys or selling newspapers, sweets, balloons etc. There are still others engaged in anti-social activities such as pick-pocketing, boot-lagging and gambling. The parents are too much pre occupied with their struggle to earn their livelihood & for survival that they have neither the time nor the economic resources to see their children through schools or to supervise their education. Illiterate themselves, they are largely unaware of the benefits of the education.

PROBLEMS OF EDUCATION OF SLUM DWELLERS

The problems of education of the urban slum children, though basically same as those of education of the poor and deprived section, are somewhat more complex. First of all, there is the problem of motivating the parents to send their children to schools. With the possibility of relatively-independent and unsupervised infancy and childhood slum children are not likely to be attracted to schools unless their parents strongly encourage and motivate them to do so. When parents themselves are uneducated, unaware and unconvinced about the value of education of, it is likely that they will function adequately as motivators.

Secondly, there is the problem of enabling the slum children to overcome the handicap of poverty. The poor economic conditions under which slum children live further interfere with their schooling. Not infrequently, a school age slum child is required to contribute to the family income or to make its own living. More often than not it hinders the child's schooling all together or at least interferes with the quality of the child's work at school. Poverty

can hold back slum children from school in other ways. For instance, they may be burdened with the household chores or responsibilities for younger siblings that make regular school attendance impossible. Not infrequently, therefore, the provision of schooling for slum children call simultaneously for action that enables them to be drawn out of the constraints of poverty. Thirdly, there is the problem of retaining those who enters schools. While development of strategies to contract the constraints of parental ignorance and apathy in general and of poverty in particular is extremely important, it is equally important to introduce in the structure of the schools, system feature that will retain the slum children in the schools. It is estimated that in India about 60% of children enrolled in class I never complete class V and 76% class VIII. Condition being unfavourable to education, in slums the dropout rate is presumably much higher than the all India figures. Illiterate and uneducated slum parents can't be accepted to be as much responsible as their better to do and educated counterparts for the retention of their children in school. The school itself should have mechanism to keep the slum child in the school. School therefore, must be made as attractive, interesting and relevant as possible to the slum children. Thus, the problem of education of the slum children is multi-faceted, on one hand parents have to be encouraged and motivated to send their children to school and it must be seen to that the education of children does not become a financial burden on the slum family. On the other hand it must be ensured that those who entered school do not leave it before they complete their schooling.

It must be accepted that the slum areas differ from other localities in socio-economic and ecological aspects. It may be therefore, unrealistic to think that education of children in slum areas can be successfully carried on in the same manner as elsewhere. It may be necessary to design special educational programme for the success of education in slum areas. Any special programme that is launched should be geared to cope with the constraints known to defeat slum schooling and should make education more suitable and convenient to them.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Tilak (1992) in his review of the status of primary education in India; discussed selected issues related to primary education in 1980s. He mentioned that despite significant quantitative expansion over last decades, primary education still suffers from inadequacy both in quantitative and qualitative terms.

Aggarwal (2001) attributed the non-retention of children to the duality of education system. He claimed that the education system does not cater to the needs of poor, unprivileged children. Many poor parents feel cheated due to irrelevant content, inadequate infrastructure and low motivation of the teachers to inculcate the necessary competencies and values among the children.

Nautiyal (1993) has highlighted the dismal performance of educational programmes in slums of Delhi and spelled out specific strategies to improve the access and utilization of basic educational facilities in these areas. He further stressed on the issues of developing indigenous approaches towards promoting education as per the prevailing needs of the people staying in the slums, and also utilizing and strengthening the institutional mechanisms already existing there.

JUSTIFICATION OF THE STUDY

The drive for universal elementary education has gained momentum during the last decade. Various initiatives and declarations have stressed the importance of achieving universal elementary education. However, the goal of universalization of elementary education still remains a distant reality. Despite several schemes and programmes in practice including the RTE, India has not been able to achieve the goal of Universalization of Elementary Education. Universal elementary education (UEE) is necessary for accelerating India's economic growth.

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A significant proportion of the children in Delhi, who are not going to schools, belong to the slum areas. Slums in Delhi have been growing very fast in the last few years. Most of the out of school children belong to these areas. As almost in each slum of Delhi, this may be the situation, it needs special attention and the reasons for non-enrolment and drop-out at elementary stage must be worked out if we are to achieve the goal of Universalization of Elementary Education. In this context the researcher would like to study the prevalent problems of non-enrolment and drop-out of slum children of 6-14 years age group of Jamia Nagar's Locality.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the socio-economic condition of the slum dwellers. It includes demographic characteristics like type and family size, whether migrated or not, gender, age; income, education and occupation of the family.
2. To study the factors responsible for non-enrolment of slum children of 6-14 years of age.
3. To study the factors responsible for drop-out of slum children of 6-14 years of age.

METHODOLOGY

Convenient sampling technique was adopted. Altogether 40 parents in all: 20 parents of non-enrolled children and 20 parents of dropout children were selected from Jamia Nagar locality which comes under the South Delhi Municipal Corporation (Delhi) were taken as sample. Information regarding economic condition, occupation, education level of the family, home environment and living condition of home were collected from household survey by using socio-economic schedule while Interview Schedule has been used to collect information from parents of non-enrolled and drop-out children. Qualitative analysis was made on the basis of observation and discussion carried out during household survey and interview. The study is delimited to slum children of 6-14 years age group in Jamia Nagar Locality (Delhi).

FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

Demographic Structure

It was found that almost 70% families were nuclear with an average family size consisting of five members. Out of the total number of households taken for the study it was found that almost 92% families were migrated from different parts of India especially from Bihar, Uttar Pradesh, West Bengal, Rajasthan, Jharkhand, or even from Madhya Pradesh. It was also found that greater percentage of fathers (12.25%) than mothers (5.75%) were absent in the families either due to death or because they have left families (separated/divorced) and settled elsewhere. Widow and separated women mostly of young age usually returns back to her maiden home and lives there along with their children. It was found that 36.28% population belonged to 6-14 years age group and total 53.96% population belonged to below 18 years age group. The earlier as well as present study have recognized that adequate, safe and secured housing is another important problem area that still persists among the slum dwellers. Dirty water over flowing through broken or cracked pipes spreads foul smell all around. These are the breeding place for diseases.

Occupation, Income and Education of the Slum dwellers

It was found that majority of the head of the families were engaged in elementary occupation where income is not only poor but also uncertain and depends upon availability of work. They were hawker, delivery man, sweeper, van puller, rickshaw puller, daily wage labourer, domestic helper, cobbler, people engaged in stitching and embroidery work and so on. Near about 20% head of the families were not engaged in any economic activities either due to old age, illness, laziness or because of drug/ alcohol addiction. Monthly income of the total number of households taken for study were broadly classified into three groups as i) not more than Rs. 3000 ii) between Rs. 3001 and Rs. 6000 and

iii) more than Rs. 6000 and it was found that almost 27% belonged to the first category, near about 60% belonged to the second group and only about 30% belonged to the third group.

CAUSES OF DROPOUT

Parents' Indifferent Attitude towards Education

- 45% of the parents are indifferent whether the child studies or not; 35% parents are not interested to send their girls to school.
- This can be accounted to the illiteracy of parents. 60% of the fathers and 90% of the mothers of the dropped out children are illiterate.
- 40% of the parents have negative attitude towards girls' education. A large number of parents believe that education for girls is not important as the girls have to finally take care of the household.

Lack of Pupil's Interest in Studies

- As many as 45% pupils are not interested in studies.
- 35% pupils face problem in comprehending the lesson taught to them in the school.

Illness

- 5% of the parents suffer from severe illness, and 10% of the children have severe health problems due to which they dropped out of school.

Death of Parents

- 10% children stopped going to school after the death of their parents as they have to look after the home.

Academic Reasons

- 60% parents think that the teachers do not pay attention to the studies of children. Many teachers are rude and unsympathetic in their attitude towards students.
- Many teachers make use of corporal punishment. RTE act strictly prohibits the use of corporal punishment and any kind of mental torture by the teachers. But still teachers do not refrain from using corporal punishment.
- Students of slum areas are discriminated by the teachers in school. The teachers are biased in their treatment towards students. The teachers very often make derogatory comments about students.

Influence of Peer Group

- 15% of the children started smoking and eating tobacco products in the company of some notorious boys. As a result, the parents withdrew their children from school.
- 10% of the students face adjustment problems in school.

CAUSES OF NON-ENROLMENT

Parent's Indifferent Attitude towards Education

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- 50% of the parents are unwilling to send their children to school. Most of the parents are poor and need hands to work and earn instead of spending money on educating them as well as on their upbringing.
- 60% of the parents have negative attitude towards girls' education. Some of mothers believe that girls should learn to do household works instead of going to school as after marriage household chores are of utmost importance.
- Many parents feel insecure about the safety of girls.
- Most of the parents are illiterate. 60% of the male parents and 50% of the female parents are illiterate. Most of the parents feel that there is no point in sending their children to school.

Lack of Pupil's Interest in Studies

- 15% of the children do not want to go to school because they feel that school life interferes with their freedom to play.

Requirement at Home

- 35% of the children (mainly girls) look after the household work while their mothers go out to work.
- 45% of the children (mainly girls) look after their younger siblings.

Illness

- 15% of the parents suffer from severe illness, and 35% of the children have severe health problems due to unhygienic surroundings.

IMPLICATIONS OF THE STUDY

- The atmosphere and facilities that the school provides could enhance or impede the chances of survival of students in the system. Thus emphasis should be on joyful learning. Teachers should move away from rote memorization and emphasis should be given on constructivist approach.
- Adult literacy programmes should be initiated in slum areas. This will help the parents in recognizing the value of education.
- Special attention should be given to the education of first generation learners. The teachers should have more positive attitude towards the education of such students so that they do not feel ignored and do not dropout.
- Periodic medical check-ups and pertinent health programmes need to be organised to ensure that children are not prevented from education due to ill-health.
- Adequate physical facilities like safe drinking water, classrooms; a motivating school environment and teaching of craft should be provided so that students feel motivated to come to school.
- Right to Education should be implemented in the true spirit. It has been found that many of the modalities of the act are violated.

CONCLUSION

The basic problem from which all other problems crop up in this slum area of Jamia Nagar Locality is acute poverty. Therefore, more and more income generation and poverty alleviation programmes should be properly implemented under strict monitoring system so that the economic condition of these vulnerable sections of the society could be improved by providing loans for self-employment. More job opportunities to be provided for wage earners. Their working hours and minimum wage have to be fixed in such a manner so that on one hand they will not be exploited and on the other hand they can meet their bare minimum necessities and lead a healthy life. To meet the problem of acute shortage of urban housing, lack of adequate infra-structure and basic services, attempt should be made by the Govt. To provide more shelter/housing to these people at low affordable prices so that they can have a decent living condition. To combat with the health and hygiene related problem children in school should be trained about the basic principles of health, hygiene and cleanliness so that they can in turn at least to some extent make other family members aware of these basic facts. It has also been found from the data there is a high degree of fusion among the various economic and social factors which affect the schooling of children in slum areas. Though household income

and per capita income have been identified as important factors influencing the participation of a child in education, there are other significant causes of non-enrolment and drop out Like high illiteracy level among the parents of slum children, pupils disinterestedness in studies, illness of family members, illness of child herself/himself, poor economic conditions, landing domestic help and taking care of siblings. Besides these, academic reasons like problem of comprehension, unsympathetic and discriminatory attitude of teachers, corporal punishment by teachers and influence of peer group also form the main reasons for drop-out of slum children before completion of elementary education. These drop-out children propagated the unsympathetic and discriminatory attitude of teachers to the other members of the slum sometimes it constraint them not to enrolled their ward in the school. So there is a need of hour to aware the slum peoples about the importance of education for the better life amenities.

REFERENCES

- Agnihotry, Pushma (1994). Poverty amidst prosperity: Survey of Slum. M.D. Publication Pvt. Ltd. N.Delhi, (P.7-10, 21-27,43-48).*
- Aikara, J.(1979). Educating out of school children: A survey of Dharavi Slum. In Buch,M.B. (ed) : Third Survey of Research in Education, 1978-83, NCERT, New Delhi, p.106.*
- Best, J.W. and Kahn, James, V. (1995). Research in Education (7th edition New Delhi: Prentice Hall of India Pvt. Ltd.*
- Bharat Bhushan, M. (1998). 'Effectiveness of slum improvement programmes and pattern of slum proliferation: A case study of Rahmat Nagar', 1998.*
- Desai, S.A. (1989). Education of the Child in Urban Slums: An overview of factors affecting learning and responsive action through social work. In the Indian Journal Social Work, Vol.-L, 1(P. 505-23).*
- Duraisamy, P. (2001) "Effectiveness of incentives on school enrolment and attainment," Journal of Educational Planning and Administration. Vol. XV, No. 2, pp. 155- 177, NIEPA, New Delhi.*
- GOI, (1986). National Policy on Education. MHRD, New Delhi.*
- Government of India (2005). Slum Population, New Delhi.*
- Government of India (2012). Census of India 2011, New Delhi.*
- Khandekar, M. (1974). A Study of Drop-outs. In the Indian Journal of Social Work, Vol. (P. 7-19, 35).*
- Ramchandran, V. (2006). 'Urban schooling mired in apathy and prejudice', Economic and political weekly, 4 February, pp. 383-384.*
- Srivastava, R.S. (1997). Access to basic education in Uttar Pradesh. Results from a household survey (mimeo. University of Allahabad.*
- Suraiya (2007-08). Non-enrolment and Dropout of Slum Children at Elementary Level. Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi.*
- UN-Habitat(2010).Retrived from www.unhabitat.org/pmss/getpage.asp?page=bookview&book=3105 dated 16.06.13.*

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Nagar Locality**

UNESCO (1996). Learning: the treasure within: Report to UNESCO of the International

Commission on Education for the twenty first century, Oxford University Press.

Zaida, S.M.I.A. (2008). ' Facilities in primary and upper primary schools in India – an analysis of DISE data of selected major states', in Journal of Educational Planning and Administration, Vol. xxii, No. 1 NIEPA, New Delhi, January. pp. 59-81.